

Master in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Extracting Sonic Trajectories

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Overview	1
1.2	Motivation	2
1.2.1	Extracting groove	2
1.2.2	Universal neural encoders are everywhere	2
1.3	Objectives	2
1.3.1	Tracking sonic trajectories	3
1.3.2	Interpretability of representations	3
1.3.3	Test bench for representations	3
1.4	Structure of the Report	3
1.4.1	State of the art	4
1.4.2	Exploratory experiments	4
1.4.3	First Study	4
1.4.4	Second Study	5
1.4.5	Conclusion	5
2	State of the art	6
2.1	Groove	6
2.2	Onset detection	7
2.2.1	Traditional approaches	7
2.2.2	Deep Learning approaches	8
2.3	Trajectories	9

2.4	Representations	9
2.4.1	Traditional representations	9
2.4.2	Latent spaces	10
3	Exploratory experiments	13
3.1	Introduction	13
3.2	Methodology	13
3.2.1	Synth	14
3.2.2	Test set	14
3.2.3	Heatmaps	15
3.2.4	Magnitude	16
3.2.5	Distance	16
3.2.6	Cosine similarity	16
3.3	Results	16
3.3.1	Amplitude	16
3.3.2	Pitch	16
3.3.3	Noise	17
3.3.4	Frequency content	18
3.3.5	Delay and reverb	20
4	Study 1: Single Modulations	22
4.1	Introduction	22
4.2	Setup	22
4.2.1	Dataset	23
4.2.2	Representations	25
4.2.3	Metrics and measurements	25
4.2.4	Procedure	27
4.3	Results	28
4.3.1	Example plot	28

4.3.2	Summary table	31
4.4	Discussion	31
5	Study 2: Double Modulations	33
5.1	Introduction	33
5.2	Setup	33
5.2.1	Dataset	34
5.2.2	Representations	36
5.2.3	Metrics and measurements	36
5.2.4	Procedure	38
5.3	Results	38
5.3.1	Example boxplots	39
5.3.2	Tables	40
5.4	Discussion	42
6	Conclusions and discussion	45
6.1	Overview	45
6.2	Representations	45
6.3	Metrics	46
6.4	First Study: Single Modulations	46
6.5	Second Study: Double Modulations	47
6.6	Future Directions	47
	List of Figures	48
	List of Tables	50
	Bibliography	51
A	Linear Analysis of Modulation Representation	53
A.1	Setup	54

A.1.1	Dataset	54
A.1.2	Methodology	54
A.1.3	Stage 1: Per-Sample Model Fitting	55
A.1.4	Stage 2: Generalization with an Average Model	55
A.2	Results	55
A.2.1	Per-Sample Model Performance	55
A.2.2	Generalization Model Performance	56
A.3	Discussion	57

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Abstract

Groove in music is more than just rhythmic onsets, it's a continuous perceptual experience shaped by subtle changes in dynamics, pitch, and timbre. Traditional audio analysis often focuses on discrete events, missing the evolving character of sound that contributes to immersion and movement. This work proposes a trajectory-based approach to audio analysis, aimed at extracting sonic trajectories: time series that represent meaningful changes in audio features over time.

To explore this idea, both traditional and modern machine learning-based audio representations are considered, including MFCC, CQT, and latent spaces from neural models such as Music2Latent and Descript Audio Codec. A library of synthetic audio signals with known modulations was developed, allowing precise ground-truth comparisons. Various metrics are used to track changes across time in these representations.

An algorithm was built to extract these trajectories by processing representation vectors through smoothing, downsampling, and convexity normalization. A test bench was created to systematically evaluate how well different representations support trajectory extraction. Results show that some latent spaces are surprisingly effective in tracking complex modulations, while others struggle with certain types of changes, such as frequency modulation or filtering.

Overall, this work demonstrates the potential of using trajectory-based methods for perceptual audio analysis and provides a framework for testing and comparing representations in a controlled and replicable way. It also raises important questions about interpretability in learned audio spaces and opens up future directions for applying this approach to real-world and creative audio systems.

Keywords: audio representation; sonic trajectories; groove; neural encoders; music information retrieval

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Overview

This work explores how to track meaningful changes in sound over time using different audio representations. The goal is to move beyond simple onset detection and capture more of what makes music feel alive and immersive, including variations in amplitude, pitch, and timbre; these variations can be modulations and envelopes, which are perceived as contours of continuous ongoing events. In this work variations that evolve through time will be called sonic trajectories, a term that highlights the report's perspective of sound as a sequence of points in a multidimensional representation.

Both traditional signal processing methods and modern machine learning-based representations are examined, including neural encoders with complex latent spaces. The aim is not only to extract these trajectories but also to understand how the information is carried, and whether these representations can be interpreted in a useful way.

The report is structured to first explain the motivation and context, then review the existing state of the art, describe exploratory experiments and two studies, which analyze sound of increasing complexity, presenting a systematic evaluation and discussion of results.

GitHub repository with all the code: [inspektral/sonic-trajectories](https://github.com/inspektral/sonic-trajectories)

1.2 Motivation

1.2.1 Extracting groove

The initial idea for this work was quite practical: building an onset detector. However, it quickly became clear that rhythm and groove are not just about onsets. Groove involves patterns, repetition, and subtle changes in sound that evolve over time. Capturing this requires tracking sonic changes as continuous trajectories rather than isolated events. In this work the main aim is to extract a single trajectory that describes the movement of the sound, which has to be perceptually relevant and correlating with the perceived movement, groove. Thinking in terms of sonic trajectories allows us to model these changes as time series, capturing how audio features such as amplitude, pitch, and timbre develop over time. This approach is more flexible and expressive, and can be useful in contexts like live performance, sound design, or any application that benefits from a richer understanding of musical movement.

1.2.2 Universal neural encoders are everywhere

At the same time, universal neural encoders and other modern audio representations have become widely available. These models often learn complex latent spaces that, while powerful, are hard to interpret. A key question is whether these spaces actually contain useful information about perceptual changes in sound—and if so, how we can extract and understand it.

1.3 Objectives

The main goal of this project is to extract perceptually meaningful trajectories from audio representations. These trajectories should reflect important changes in sound over time, going beyond simple amplitude envelopes to include pitch and timbral variations.

1.3.1 Tracking sonic trajectories

Designing a process that can follow how sound evolves continuously rather than just marking discrete events. This includes building metrics and processing steps that can capture subtle changes in timbre, pitch modulation, or dynamic envelopes. The idea is to create a more meaningful kind of envelope follower that is aware of multiple audio dimensions and can operate in real time or offline, depending on the application.

1.3.2 Interpretability of representations

Many modern audio representations, especially those learned by neural networks, offer powerful but opaque latent spaces. This work aims to explore whether these representations actually contain useful information about perceptual changes in sound, and whether it is possible to develop some intuition about how they work. By extracting trajectories, we hope to "read" these spaces in a way that makes sense both technically and musically.

1.3.3 Test bench for representations

Building a systematic way to evaluate and compare different representations for this purpose. The goal is to create a flexible framework that can measure how well a given representation supports trajectory extraction. This involves defining metrics for success (like correlation with ground-truth modulation), identifying strengths and weaknesses, and making it easier to test both existing and future representations in a consistent way.

1.4 Structure of the Report

The report is subdivided into the following chapters:

- State of the art: review of existing literature and techniques.
- Exploratory experiments: early tests using controlled synthetic sounds.

- First study: systematic evaluation of single modulations.
- Second study: systematic evaluation of double modulations.
- Conclusion: summary of findings, limitations, and possible future directions.

1.4.1 State of the art

This chapter reviews the main concepts and previous work relevant to this project. It starts with the idea of groove in music, both from a theoretical and perceptual perspective. It then covers traditional and deep learning approaches to onset detection, discusses the notion of sonic trajectories for sound analysis, and surveys various audio representations, both classic signal-processing methods and modern neural latent spaces, that can be used for trajectory extraction.

1.4.2 Exploratory experiments

This section describes initial experiments using synthesized audio signals with known modulations. The goal is to see if different representations can capture these modulations in a meaningful way. These experiments help motivate the choice of representations and metrics, and offer an early look at the strengths and weaknesses of each approach before developing the main algorithm.

1.4.3 First Study

This chapter presents a systematic evaluation of single modulations. A dataset of synthetic sounds was generated with one parameter modulated at a time; amplitude, frequency, filter cutoff, or oscillator shape. For each case, trajectories were extracted and compared with ground-truth signals through correlation measures. The goal is to establish a baseline, showing the sensitivity and stability of different representations under simple and isolated conditions.

1.4.4 Second Study

This chapter extends the evaluation to double modulations. Two parameters vary simultaneously, creating interactions between trajectories. The analysis focuses on how metrics respond when modulations overlap or interfere, and whether one can still be reliably tracked in the presence of another. The aim is to test robustness and generalization of representations under more complex and realistic scenarios.

1.4.5 Conclusion

The final chapter summarizes the main findings of the project, discussing what worked, what didn't, and why. It reflects on the usability of different representations, the usefulness of the developed metrics and procedures, and the overall potential of this approach for audio analysis and creative applications. It also suggests directions for further research, including improvements to the testing framework and application to real-world audio.

Chapter 2

State of the art

This chapter illustrates the current state of the art of the various topics pertinent to the work, it is divided into 2 groups of sections, the first group reviews the concept of groove from a more theoretical point of view, covering the psychoacoustical and cognitive aspects (Section 2.1) and proceeds to go over past and current technical approaches for onset detection (Section 2.2), which is the most relevant MIR topic related to groove. The second group is an overview of the idea of sonic trajectories (Section 2.3), which is one of the scopes used for music analysis, especially for the more experimental genres, where most of the structures are built on timbral aspects of sound and proceeds to present various more technical representations and algorithms (Section 2.4) used to analyze sound and music especially from a timbral perspective that can be useful for a trajectory-based interpretation of sound.

2.1 Groove

In the musicology discourse, groove is an important concept, yet elusive and multifaceted, depending on genres, eras, and contexts. It is closely related to the idea of rhythm, musical gesture, dance, immersion, and is deeply correlated with motor areas of the brain, as explained by Etani [1]. Defining groove is not a simple task, several definitions have been proposed, an interesting general one that should be taken into account was proposed by Duman et al. in 2024 [2]: “Groove is a par-

ticipatory experience (related to immersion, movement, positive affect, and social connection) resulting from subtle interaction of specific music- (such as time- and pitch-related features), performance-, and/or individual-related factors.”. It is thus clear that groove is an incredibly wide term, for our purposes it had been narrowed down to computable rhythmic audio features, in the literature [3] mainly related to percussive elements and more generally events that provide a perceptual quantization of time. In the field of MIR those events are mainly treated with various onset detection techniques.

2.2 Onset detection

Onset detection refers to the process of locating the beginning of a musical note or sound, often associated with the transient phase where the signal exhibits rapid changes. It is essential for applications such as automatic music transcription, beat tracking, and synchronization in music production. The task is particularly challenging in polyphonic music, where multiple instruments play simultaneously, leading to overlapping signals.

2.2.1 Traditional approaches

Traditional digital signal processing methods for onset detection rely on analyzing various signal properties to detect abrupt changes indicative of onsets [4]. These can be categorized into several sub-approaches depending on the audio representation used:

Time domain

A common technique is energy-based detection, where the signal’s energy is calculated over short windows, and onsets are identified when energy exceeds a predefined threshold [4]. For example, detecting sudden increases in amplitude is straightforward but can lead to false positives in noisy or amplitude-modulated signals.

Frequency domain

These involve the transformation of the signal into the frequency domain using techniques such as the fast Fourier transform (FFT). Metrics such as spectral flux [4], which measures the rate of change in spectral energy between consecutive frames, are widely used. Other metrics include spectral centroid, tracking the center of mass of the spectrum, which can highlight frequency shifts at onsets. These methods are more robust than time-domain approaches but require more computational resources due to FFT processing. Superflux is in this category of onset detection algorithms and is the most widely used, as it is a standard go to for Librosa and Essentia, the most widespread MIR toolkits. Other advanced methods of this kind take into account also phase changes of the components, detecting onsets when simultaneous changes in phase occur.

2.2.2 Deep Learning approaches

Deep learning methods, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have gained prominence in onset detection by leveraging neural networks to learn patterns directly from data, often represented as spectrograms or other transforms (wavelet, CQT). They learn spatial patterns that correspond to onsets, such as sudden changes in frequency content. A notable early example is the work by Schlüter and Böck [5], which showed CNNs outperforming traditional methods on a dataset with 26,000 annotated onsets. RNNs, in particular LSTMs are also able to outperform traditional methods, as shown by Marchi et al. [6]. Nowadays most advanced models use a combination of the two, as shown by one of the most advanced models for polyphonic strings onset detection developed in 2023 [7]. It is important to note that although those models outperform traditional methods the costs to develop them are very high, both from a computational point of view and data sourcing wise. Running them is also expensive, GPU acceleration might be needed and not all of them can run in real time on a common laptop. In the vast panorama of onset detection models Dance Dance Convolution is the one used as of today by the system, it is based on a convolution architecture trained on Dance Dance Revolution

annotations and shows outstanding real-time performance for transient-like onset detection. This is ideal for detecting percussive sounds but falls short when onsets are softer or happen in the pitch or timbre domain.

2.3 Trajectories

Sound gestures and trajectories in sound art and electroacoustic music refer to how sounds move and evolve, capturing both performer actions and spatial dynamics. Smalley's spectromorphology [8], introduced in 1986, describes the temporal shaping of sound spectra, providing a tool to analyze these aspects. While Smalley describes them from an analytical point of view, composers have been using similar concepts representing them with graphic notation. This notation uses visual symbols to represent music, offering flexibility beyond traditional notation. Xenakis's UPIC system translates drawings into sound, while Cardew's "Treatise" (1967) leaves interpretation open, both influencing sound gestures (Xenakis UPIC, Cardew Treatise). MIR techniques model and generate music by computational representations that collide with the ones used by musicologists and composers. Though direct research is sparse, the integration of those representations could lead to interesting results.

2.4 Representations

Sound representations are methods used to transform raw audio signals into structured formats that emphasize specific characteristics, making it easier to analyze, process, or interpret the audio data. They are essential in fields like audio processing, speech recognition, music analysis, and machine learning for audio-related tasks. Each representation highlights different aspects of sound—such as amplitude, frequency, or abstract features—depending on the intended application.

2.4.1 Traditional representations

Traditional representations focus on decomposing audio signals into interpretable components, often based on frequency or perceptual scales. These methods are

well-established and widely used in signal processing.

Fourier transform

The Fourier Transform decomposes a signal into its frequency components, and for audio, the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) is commonly used to capture how these frequencies evolve over time [4]. It divides the audio into short segments and computes the Fourier Transform for each, resulting in a time-frequency representation.

Constant Q Transform

The Constant Q Transform is a time-frequency representation where each frequency bin has a constant Q factor, meaning the bandwidth is proportional to the frequency. This results in a logarithmic frequency scale, aligning with human perception of pitch. Unlike STFT, which uses linear frequency spacing, CQT uses logarithmic spacing, with lower frequencies having narrower bandwidths and higher frequencies having wider bandwidths [9]. This is particularly effective for musical signals.

Nonnegative Matrix Factorization

NMF is a matrix decomposition technique that factors a non-negative matrix (e.g., a spectrogram) into two non-negative matrices: a dictionary matrix (basis spectra) and an activation matrix (how these bases are activated over time). This can be interpreted as representing the audio as a combination of basis spectra. This representation is widely used in the MIR field especially for source separation.

2.4.2 Latent spaces

Latent space representations leverage machine learning, particularly neural networks, to create abstract, high-level representations of data [10]. These are often used for tasks requiring similarity measurements, semantic understanding, generation, or compression, and they represent a shift toward data-driven approaches.

CLAP and semantics

Using contrastive learning, it is possible to learn mappings between audio clips and their textual descriptions into a shared embedding space where related concepts, like the sound of rain and the phrase "rain falling", are close together, and unrelated ones are far apart. This cross-modal approach bridges the gap between sound and meaning, enabling tasks like searching for audio with text or understanding audio content semantically, thus building a very semantically rich and meaningful latent space, the downside is that long samples are needed, and these embeddings cannot be calculated frame in real-time, content is therefore very meaningful and rich, but temporal resolution in today's models is very poor. CLAP [11] is the most widespread model that has been trained in this way and its architecture enables cross-modal tasks like typing "dog barking" to find a sound clip or feeding an audio file to get a text description. Its contrastive learning approach also allows zero-shot classification: you can classify audio into categories never seen during training by using text labels (e.g., "happy music" vs. "sad music"). By focusing on high-level semantics, CLAP makes audio understandable in human terms, which is a crucial for applications like content retrieval or audio annotation.

RAVE and live use

Some models focus on real-time audio synthesis and manipulation via latent spaces. they usually leverage a variational autoencoder (VAE) type of neural network that learns a compressed, probabilistic representation of data to capture the essence of audio in a way that's both efficient and flexible. The idea here is to encode audio into a compact "latent space" and then decode it back into sound, enabling not just reconstruction but also the creation of new audio. This makes them useful for generative applications, such as synthesizing new sounds or morphing existing ones, all while keeping latency low enough for live use. A well known example is RAVE [12] that uses an architecture that shines for real-time performance and is optimized to process audio fast enough for live applications like music production or interactive sound design. Its generative nature means that the latent space can

be sampled to create entirely new sounds or tweak the latent variables to transfer styles (e.g., making a drum sound like a synth).

SoundStream and compression

Another use of latent spaces is for building neural audio codecs built for efficient compression and high-quality reconstruction. The goal is to shrink audio into a compact form for storage or streaming while keeping it sounding great when played back. The result is a very fast and complete latent space but it is optimized for compression, not for understandability and semantics. A successful example is SoundStream [13], which is trained end-to-end with neural networks, combining compression, quantization, and perceptual quality optimization into one seamless system. It's designed to work in real time and adapt to different compression needs. SoundStream's architecture supports variable bitrates and its real-time efficiency means it can encode and decode on the fly, perfect for streaming.

Chapter 3

Exploratory experiments

3.1 Introduction

The idea of this set of experiments is to examine different representations with synthesized signals in which some modulation occurs and visualize if there is some correlation between the representation's vectors and the modulation. The representations considered are STFT spectrum, MFCCs, CQT for the traditional side, DAC and Music2Latent latent spaces for the machine learning side. Those representations have been chosen firstly based on widespread adoption, novelty and performance. In particular STFT is the most used transform for MIR related processing, MFCC is also widely used and the data compression it performs packs the information in very small vectors. CQT is chosen because of its psychoacoustical and musical relevance. The two neural encoders are very different DAC is made for data compression, works on raw audio with very high time resolution, music2latent is instead trained on complex spectrograms. Those two were chosen as examples of good performing, recent but also very different neural representations.

3.2 Methodology

The methodology involves visually inspecting the representations to determine if there is an apparent correlation between the modulation signal and movements in

the latent space.

3.2.1 Synth

In order to have a test set of sounds with the modulation signals used for their generations, a small library to synthesize sounds with sample by sample modulation has been built. In this way it is possible to have both the audio signal and the control signals that function as a ground truth. The library is capable of generating sounds with various waveshapes, apply audio rate modulation, filtering distortion, reverb and delay effects, with audio rate modulation on all the main parameters.

3.2.2 Test set

13 tests were written, each one is 10s long, 44100 samples per second (Code and audio):

- Square slow attack: 4 2.5s 440hz square wave long notes, triangular envelope
- Square short: short burst (1200 samples) 44hz square wave, exponential envelope
- Square vibrato: continuous square wave oscillating between 330 and 550, vibrato starts at 0.2hz and rises to 1hz
- Sawtooth over noise: 4 1.5s long 50hz sawtooth notes, with fast attack and slow decay, over white noise with half the amplitude (-6db) with respect to the sawtooth
- Sines over noise: 4 1.5s long notes made of 11 stacked sines each one with a stable random frequency between 100hz and 5000hz, with fast attack and slow decay, over white noise with half the amplitude (-6db) with respect to the sawtooth
- Filtered saw: stable 100hz saw with 12db/oct lowpass filter with cutoff frequency between 700hz and 1300hz, modulated by 1hz sine wave

- Soft clipped triangle: stable 440hz triangle wave into a soft clipper with gain between 0db and 20db, modulated by a sine wave that starts at 0.2hz and ends at 1hz
- FM triangle (modulator amplitude): stable 440hz triangle wave with modulated by 600hz triangle wave whose amplitude is modulated between 0 and 0.5 by a sine wave that starts at 0.2hz and ends at 1hz
- FM triangle (modulator frequency): stable 440hz triangle wave with modulated by 400-600hz (modulated by a sine wave that starts at 0.2hz and ends at 1hz) triangle wave with amplitude 0.5.
- Noise with delay: short burst of noise with delay (0.1s, 0.7 feedback) with wet between 0 and 0.5, modulated by a sine wave that starts at 0.2hz and ends at 1hz
- Sawtooth with delay: short burst of 220hz sawtooth with delay (0.1s, 0.7 feedback) with wet between 0 and 0.5, modulated by a sine wave that starts at 0.2hz and ends at 1hz
- Noise with reverb: short burst of noise with reverb (1.5 decay, flat response) with wet between 0 and 0.5, modulated by a sine wave that starts at 0.2hz and ends at 1hz
- Sawtooth with reverb: short burst of 220hz sawtooth with reverb (1.5 decay, flat response) with wet between 0 and 0.5, modulated by a sine wave that starts at 0.2hz and ends at 1hz

3.2.3 Heatmaps

for every representation a heatmap is plotted, for the stft it is a common spectrogram for other representations it is something similar. This heatmap helps in understanding the temporal resolution of the representation and to understand if there is some structure and correlation between the dimensions. If a variation that highly correlates with the modulation appears in the heatmap then it should be

possible to extract it. This however might not be generalizable to many signals and different modulations, which is crucial for our objectives.

3.2.4 Magnitude

Magnitude is calculated as a time series of the vectors Frobenius norm.

3.2.5 Distance

Distance between each vector and the previous is calculated.

3.2.6 Cosine similarity

Cosine similarity between each vector and the previous is calculated.

3.3 Results

The following are some interesting results of the experiments, shown especially to clarify what is going on. The presented examples are not comprehensive by any means, and should be taken as basic case studies of various modulations in various representations.

3.3.1 Amplitude

Amplitude is present in most representations in a quite straightforward way, and it is very easy to extract from any of the ones that are being used in this project. An example of tracking amplitude with music2latent is provided.

3.3.2 Pitch

Pitch is another of the most important characteristics of sound, many tools have been developed to track pitch and we don't expect to outperform those, most of straightforward representations, without additional processing lead to quite poor results further inquiries with spectral flux and other methods could be interesting

Figure 1: music2latent vector magnitudes easily tracks amplitude

expansions but are considered out of scope for this work. It is interesting to note that DAC is one of the best-performing representations for this task, which is surprising given its small (64-sample) window.

Figure 2: CQT shows some repeating patterns

3.3.3 Noise

An interesting characteristic of neural encoders is that, being trained on audio that contains a lot of pitched content, they are particularly good at ignoring noise. In this example, it can be seen that the magnitude of the vectors in music2latent tracks the amplitude of the sawtooth oscillator without any problems, even if the signal is very noisy.

Figure 3: DAC clearly moves when pitch is not stable

Figure 4: music2latent vector magnitudes easily tracks inharmonic sines over noise

3.3.4 Frequency content

Frequency content of a signal can be altered in many ways, since the developed synthesizer is quite simple for these preliminary experiments the methods that have been considered are: lowpass filtering, soft clipping, frequency modulation.

Lowpass filter

Lowpass filters are one of the most used and most modulated processes in electronic music, and it is so one of the ones we're most interested in. Tracking it is not that difficult; it can be done also with a simple vocoder, and supposedly any frequency

domain representation, like cqt or music2latent can do it, as shown below.

Figure 5: Low pass filter affects CQT distances

Figure 6: Low pass filter impact on music2latent magnitude

Clipping

Clipping is another very common process often modulated in many contexts, the result is roughly similar to filtering and it can also be tracked by frequency domain based representations:

Figure 7: music2latent vector magnitudes easily tracks soft clipping

Frequency modulation

A more tricky way to alter the frequency content is frequency modulation, which can be modulated both in quantity (amplitude of the modulator) and in quality (frequency of the modulator). The results might be less obvious and underrepre-

sented with respect to distortion and filtering but since it is still a frequency-related phenomenon it seems quite trackable by frequency domain representations.

Figure 8: Impact of fm amount on CQT magnitude

Figure 9: Impact of fm amount on music2latent similarity

Figure 10: cqt vector magnitudes

3.3.5 Delay and reverb

Delay and reverb are maybe the least interesting aspect, since there are already many ways to remove reverb, also in real-time and the difference between the energy between reverb and direct signal clearly correlates with the amount of reverb. Nevertheless, it is interesting to see how those kinds of processing appears in the latent space and other representations.

Figure 11: music2latent magnitudes

Figure 12: DAC magnitudes

Chapter 4

Study 1: Single Modulations

4.1 Introduction

This first study focuses on very simple cases, in order to give an idea of what the various representations can achieve, if a metric scores low on those tests, it is unlikely that it will be useful on more complex tasks. The idea is straightforward: using basic synthesized sound in which one single parameter is modulated with a smooth curve, different representations(series of vectors), are then calculated and those metrics(time series) extracted and correlation between the metric and the modulation applied. If the correlation is high (close to 1.0 the metric is able to track the modulation).

Jupyter notebook available at: [sonic-trajectories/blob/main/study-1.ipynb](#)

4.2 Setup

This section describes the setup of the experiment, focusing on the dataset of synthesized sounds and then listing representations and metrics used. All the processing applied is explained in detail in order to ensure replicability.

4.2.1 Dataset

The dataset is fully synthesized with minisynth, a tiny library developed for the occasion.

The library is available at: pypi.org/project/minisynth/

MiniSynthSubtractive

The synthesizer used is a single oscillator subtractive (non-resonant lowpass 12db/oct) synthesizer with 4 parameters:

- Base frequency (exponential mapping [50hz – 1000hz]): this is the base frequency of the oscillator
- Amplitude (exponential mapping [0.0 – 1.0]): the amplitude of the signal
- Filter cutoff(exponential mapping [200hz – 5000hz]): cutoff frequency of the lowpass filter
- Wave mix (linear mapping [0.0 – 1.0]): the mix between square and sawtooth waves

This architecture has been chosen because even in it's very minimal design it is able to produce a good variety of sonic trajectories, directly associated with the parameters:

- Absolute pitch: the base frequency knob can control the absolute vertical placement in the spectrum, in a perceptual relevant range and mapping.
- Amplitude: this directly controls the amplitude of the singla in a perceptually relevant mapping.
- Absolute spectrum shape: the filter cutoff controls the absolute shape of the spectrum, mainly in the part that contains harmonics.

- Relative spectrum shape: the wave mix is able to change the balance between odd and even harmonics changing the relative shape of the spectrum with respect to the fundamental.

Additionally the synthesizer is implemented so that any parameter can be modulated at sample rate speed.

The sounds

The dataset consists of 1620 2s long sounds, a little less than 1h in total. For every sound one single parameter is positively modulated with a single cycle of a cosine wave at 5 different level of modulation amount: (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5) of their respective ranges. For example the amplitude of a sound with an amplitude base level of 0.25 with a 0.2 modulation amount will start at 0.45 decrease to 0.25 and rise back to 0.45 in parameter range terms, in actual amplitude those values would be exponentially mapped ($0.25 = 0.1, 0.45 = 0.23$).

The base values of the non-modulated parameters can be one of the three between 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 of the parameter range and the modulated parameter base can be one of the three between 0.0, 0.25, 0.50 to account for the additive modulation.

The complete dataset consists of all the possible combinations of the aforementioned settings: 3 levels for each one of the four parameters, 4 possible modulation targets, 5 possible modulation amounts:

$$3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 4 \times 5 = 1620$$

In this way, even if just on a minimal set of points per parameter, it is easy to understand the interactions and the dependencies between various parameters. It is to be mentioned, though, that some representations (DAC in our case) work on raw audio and representations have a periodicity based on the ratio between the fundamental frequency in the sound and the window size and so they behave differently at different frequencies and the results of the experiment could vary due

to this phenomenon. Since those type of representations are quite widespread for compression tasks, further investigation on these issues could have interesting and potentially useful results.

The direct consequence of the dataset that contains all the possible combinations of a small set of possibilities is that the dataset is actually not stored anywhere and can be generated directly, possibly with just an iterator and it is thus just a tiny algorithm with ranges and mappings. That said in the actual study intermediate steps have been saved for validation and debugging purposes.

4.2.2 Representations

The representations used are:

- FFT spectrogram: $w = 4096, h = 512$ hann window
- MFCCs: 20 coefficients $w = 2048, h = 512$ hann window
- CQT: in db $h = 512$
- DAC: provided compressed latents (72 dimensions) are used
- music2latent: 4 encoders shifted by 1024 to achieve 4x oversampling

4.2.3 Metrics and measurements

On every representation the following metrics are calculated:

Magnitude

Frobenius norm of vectors as a time series:

$$M_t = \|\mathbf{x}_t\|_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_{t,i})^2}$$

Cosine similarity

Cosine similarity between subsequent vectors:

$$S_t = \frac{\mathbf{a}_t \cdot \mathbf{b}_t}{\|\mathbf{a}_t\|_2 \|\mathbf{b}_t\|_2 + \varepsilon} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n a_{t,i} b_{t,i}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n a_{t,i}^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n b_{t,i}^2} + \varepsilon}$$

Distances

Distances between subsequent vectors:

$$D_t = \|\mathbf{x}_{t+1} - \mathbf{x}_t\|_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_{t+1,i} - x_{t,i})^2}$$

Processing

Every metric is smoothed with a flat window $0.25s$, which ensures the permanence of the sub-audio rate changes and removes most of the noise, normalized in the range $[0, 1]$ and stretched to fit the modulator length ($l = 1000$)

1. **Smoothing with a flat window of length w (corresponding to $0.25 s$):**

$$\tilde{m}[t] = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{k=-(w-1)/2}^{(w-1)/2} m[t+k]$$

2. **Normalization to the range $[0, 1]$:**

$$\hat{m}[t] = \frac{\tilde{m}[t] - \min(\tilde{m})}{\max(\tilde{m}) - \min(\tilde{m})}$$

3. **Stretching to fit modulator length $l = 1000$:**

$$m_{\text{resampled}}[n] = \hat{m} \left[\frac{n}{l} \cdot N \right], \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, l-1$$

Correlation

Correlation, in the form of pearson correlation coefficient, is the best indicator of the accuracy of the extraction. Perfect correlation ($\rho = 1$) means that the output of the algorithm is linearly related to the modulator. It is defined as:

$$\rho_{x,y} = \frac{\text{cov}(x, y)}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}$$

Polarity can be flipped, depending on the representation and on the specific feature, since we are interesting in matching mainly the movement it makes sense to consider:

$$|\text{corr}(a(x), m)|$$

4.2.4 Procedure

The procedure for the experiment is the following:

1. Generate all the possible combinations of parameters (stored in a pandas dataframe).
2. Synthesize the sounds from the parameters and calculate each representation, for each representatio a h5 file is created and the indexed representations are stored. This is done because the encoding step, especially for neural representations, is more computationally intensive.
3. For each entry in each representation (5×1620) the three metrics are calculated, smoothed and correlation with the cosine is computed. The result of this process is a dataframe with 15 correlation columns, one for every metric-representation pair.
4. boxplots are generated, filtering the dataframe based on what parameter is modulated and grouped by the other variables.

4.3 Results

In order to understand the results several boxplots have been produced, the full set can be examined in the notebook(sonic-trajectories/blob/main/study-1.ipynb). In every boxplot only the data with a single representation, metric and modulation target is considered, for example a boxplot could contain the correlations of the magnitude of mfcc for amplitude modulation. In each boxplot correlation sits on the y axis, on the x axis the variable of which we are testing the influence is placed. In this way we can have a clear idea of how sensitive the representation is, for example we can understand how much modulation is needed to be sensed, and if the sensitivity changes across frequencies, amplitudes, etc.

4.3.1 Example plot

The following are a set of plots that are what is used in this study to understand which metric is the best to track filter cutoff modulations and how other variables influence the tracking. Every plot is now described in detail to understand how to read those and the ones contained in the appendix.

In all the five figures correlation for filter cutoff is plotted on the y axis, this means that we are considering only samples in which filter cutoff modulation is happening, no other modulation is applied on this subset of samples. Those samples, as those with other targets of modulations, represent a fourth of the 405, and all the combinations of variables as previously explained while having filter cutoff modulation.

Figure 13: music2latent filter cutoff modulation against modulation amount

The plot in figure 13 has the modulation amount on the x axis and we can see the impact on the tracking, it is clear that the amount of modulation influences the tracking done via magnitude, but the one done with cosine similarity is not really affected. Of all the metrics, and this will be confirmed by other plots, the distances seems the best to track filter cutoff modulation with music2latent representations.

Figure 14: music2latent filter cutoff modulation against amplitude

In the second plot(Figure 14) on the x axis the amplitude is plotted, the levels correspond to 0.25,0.50,0.75 of the range, exponentially mapped. Magnitude is highly sensitive to amplitude, the average correlation rises from 0.5 to 0.8, the other metrics are not particularly influenced by the variation in amplitude, and are thus more stable. Similarly to the previous plot, distances is the best performing metric.

Figure 15: music2latent filter cutoff modulation against frequency

For the third plot(Figure 15) on the x axis the base frequency is plotted, the levels correspond to 0.25,0.50,0.75 of the range, exponentially mapped. This is the more chaotic plot of the five, for magnitude correlation is at its highest at low frequencies,

at higher frequencies it is the worst performing. Correlation via distances increases with higher frequencies. The cosine similarity part is quite messy and to understand what is going on it is necessary to have more than only three frequency parameters possibilities.

Figure 16: music2latent filter cutoff modulation against oscillator wave shape

The plot in figure 16 has the oscillator's wave shape on the x axis and we can see the impact on the tracking, richer waves make the tracking harder for magnitude but for distances and cosine similarity they slightly improve the performance.

Figure 17: music2latent filter cutoff modulation against filter cutoff frequency

The last plot (figure 17) is the most interesting and less obvious, for tracking filter cutoff in music2latent, the single most relevant is by far the range of the filter cutoff frequency itself, in which in this case we have one the x axis. Probably for low cutoff frequencies music2latent is the best way to track cutoff frequencies of all the methods tested in this study. It is important that for this case since the modulation is happening on the parameter on the x axis, x axes value represent the centerpoints of the range around which the modulation is happening.

Modulated Parameter	frequency	amplitude	filter cutoff	oscillator shape	ALL
STFT Magnitude	0.62	0.77	0.83	<i>0.42</i>	0.66
STFT Distances	0.64	0.74	0.78	0.48	0.66
STFT Similarity	0.62	0.85	0.89	0.55	0.73
DAC Magnitude	0.48	<i>0.52</i>	0.63	0.47	<i>0.52</i>
DAC Distances	<i>0.46</i>	0.78	0.74	0.45	0.61
DAC Similarity	0.57	0.78	0.65	0.49	0.62
M2L Magnitude	0.53	0.61	0.61	0.64	0.60
M2L Distances	0.63	0.88	0.77	0.61	0.72
M2L Similarity	0.61	0.89	0.74	0.44	0.67
CQT Magnitude	0.52	0.93	0.90	0.60	0.74
CQT Distances	0.75	0.81	0.75	0.67	0.74
CQT Similarity	0.74	0.78	0.75	0.64	0.73
MFCC Magnitude	0.45	0.91	0.96	0.49	0.70
MFCC Distances	0.64	0.55	<i>0.60</i>	0.60	0.60
MFCC Similarity	0.62	0.62	0.63	0.58	0.61

Table 1: Averages of the correlations with **best** and *worst*, 1.0 is perfect correlation, 0.0 is no correlation

4.3.2 Summary table

The following is a table containing all the aggregated averages, for every modulated parameter, and each metric in each representation. Best performance on tracking each specific modulation is in **bold** and worst is in *italic*. The following section will discuss this table in depth, because even if it is a good summary it doesn't really address pitfalls and vulnerabilities of the representations.

4.4 Discussion

It appears from the table above that for simple cases such only one modulation traditional transforms are actually the way to go, in particular CQT very robust and CQT distances never perform in the bottom half, so for these basic cases it is the best choice. An interesting weak spot of CQT distances is the performance at tracking frequency modulations when the modulation is very light, this is due to the fact that at low modulation rate the energy is not moving from a bin to the next. The best performer for those cases is actually still CQT but in magnitude instead of distances (see Fig. 18).

Figure 18: CQT and frequency modulation

Another expected best performer is the MFCC representation for filter cutoff, MFCC are a summary of the absolute shape of the spectrum and it is no surprise that they are the best way to track it (see Fig. 19).

Figure 19: MFCC and filter cutoff modulation

Neural encoders(DAC and Music2Latent) based metrics didn't perform particularly well, especially DAC, which is the worst performer overall, this case is somewhat expected, since its latent space is not structured and the model is made for compression and not for MIR tasks. On the other side Music2Latent is designed for MIR tasks, and it performs similarly to STFT but with a much smaller vector size (64 against 4096), anyway, on those simple tasks, it doesn't outperform CQT.

Chapter 5

Study 2: Double Modulations

5.1 Introduction

This second study extends the evaluation to double modulations, building on the simple cases from the first study to test the representations under more complex and realistic scenarios. The idea is to see how robust the different metrics and representations are when two parameters are modulated simultaneously, creating interactions and interference between the sonic trajectories. The analysis focuses on how metrics respond when modulations overlap and whether one trajectory can still be reliably tracked in the presence of another. The aim is to test the generalization of these methods under more challenging conditions.

Jupyter notebook available at: [sonic-trajectories/blob/main/study-2.ipynb](#)

5.2 Setup

This section describes the setup of the experiment, focusing on the dataset of synthesized sounds and then listing representations and metrics used. All the processing applied is explained in detail in order to ensure replicability.

5.2.1 Dataset

The dataset is fully synthesized with minisynth, a tiny library developed for the occasion.

The library is available at: pypi.org/project/minisynth/

MiniSynthSubtractive

The synthesizer used is a single oscillator subtractive (non-resonant lowpass 12db/oct) synthesizer with 4 parameters:

- Base frequency (exponential mapping [50hz – 1000hz]): this is the base frequency of the oscillator
- Amplitude (exponential mapping [0.0 – 1.0]): the amplitude of the signal
- Filter cutoff(exponential mapping [200hz – 5000hz]): cutoff frequency of the lowpass filter
- Wave mix (linear mapping [0.0 – 1.0]): the mix between square and sawtooth waves

This architecture has been chosen because even in it's very minimal design it is able to produce a good variety of sonic trajectories, directly associated with the parameters:

- Absolute pitch: the base frequency knob can control the absolute vertical placement in the spectrum, in a perceptual relevant range and mapping.
- Amplitude: this directly controls the amplitude of the signal in a perceptually relevant mapping.
- Absolute spectrum shape: the filter cutoff controls the absolute shape of the spectrum, mainly in the part that contains harmonics

- Relative spectrum shape: the wave mix is able to change the balance between odd and even harmonics changing the relative shape of the spectrum with respect to the fundamental

Additionally the synthesizer is implemented so that any parameter can be modulated at sample rate speed.

The sounds

The dataset consists of 4374 2s long sounds, roughly 2.5h in total. For every sound two parameters are positively modulated with a single cycle of a cosine wave at three different level of modulation amount: (0.25, 0.50, 0.75) of their respective ranges, for every couple of parameters the total amount is 1.00, so if amplitude and frequency are being modulated and amplitude modulation amount is 0.25 then frequency modulation amount will be 0.75. In order to better understand the interaction between the modulations the modulation can be phase shifted: the first modulation phase is always 0, the second can be one in $(0, \frac{\pi}{2}, \pi)$. As for the first study the values are mapped to the range linearly or exponentially depending on the parameter, 0.0 is the lower limit of the range and 1.0 the upper one.

The base values of the non-modulated parameters can be one of the three between 0.25, 0.50, 0.75 of the parameter range and the modulated parameters base can be one of the three between 0.0, 0.25, 0.50 to account for the positive modulation.

The complete dataset consists of all the possible combinations of the aforementioned settings: 3 levels for each one of the four parameters, 6 possible modulated couples, 3 possible modulation amounts, 3 possible phase shifts:

$$3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 6 \times 3 \times 3 = 4374$$

As for the first study the dataset contains all the possible combinations and does not need to be stored anywhere, since it can be generated directly.

5.2.2 Representations

The representations used are:

- FFT spectrogram: $w = 4096, h = 512$ hann window
- MFCCs: 20 coefficients $w = 2048, h = 512$ hann window
- CQT: in db $h = 512$
- DAC: provided compressed latents (72 dimensions) are used
- music2latent: 4 encoders shifted by 1024 to achieve 4x oversampling

5.2.3 Metrics and measurements

On every representation the following metrics are calculated:

Magnitude

Frobenius norm of vectors as a time series:

$$M_t = \|\mathbf{x}_t\|_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_{t,i})^2}$$

Cosine similarity

Cosine similarity between subsequent vectors:

$$S_t = \frac{\mathbf{a}_t \cdot \mathbf{b}_t}{\|\mathbf{a}_t\|_2 \|\mathbf{b}_t\|_2 + \varepsilon} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n a_{t,i} b_{t,i}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n a_{t,i}^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n b_{t,i}^2} + \varepsilon}$$

Distances

Distances between subsequent vectors:

$$D_t = \|\mathbf{x}_{t+1} - \mathbf{x}_t\|_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_{t+1,i} - x_{t,i})^2}$$

Processing

Every metric is smoothed with a flat 0.25s window, this ensures that we're keeping the sub-audio rate changes and remove most of the noise, normalized in the range $[0, 1]$ and stretched to fit the modulator length ($l = 1000$)

1. **Smoothing with a flat window of length w (corresponding to 0.25 s):**

$$\tilde{m}[t] = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{k=-(w-1)/2}^{(w-1)/2} m[t+k]$$

2. **Normalization to the range $[0, 1]$:**

$$\hat{m}[t] = \frac{\tilde{m}[t] - \min(\tilde{m})}{\max(\tilde{m}) - \min(\tilde{m})}$$

3. **Stretching to fit modulator length $l = 1000$:**

$$m_{\text{resampled}}[n] = \hat{m} \left[\frac{n}{l} \cdot N \right], \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, l - 1$$

Correlation

Correlation, in the form of a Pearson correlation coefficient, is the best indicator of the accuracy of the extraction. Perfect correlation ($\rho = 1$) means that the output of the algorithm is linearly related to the modulator. It is defined as:

$$\rho_{x,y} = \frac{\text{cov}(x,y)}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}$$

Polarity can be flipped, depending on the representation and on the specific feature, since we are interested in matching mainly the movement, it makes sense to consider:

$$|corr(a(x), m)|$$

.

5.2.4 Procedure

The procedure for the experiment is the following:

1. Generate all the possible combinations of parameters (stored in a pandas dataframe)
2. Synthesize the sounds from the parameters and calculate each representation, for each representation a h5 file is created and the indexed representations are stored. This is done because the encoding step, especially for neural representations, is more computationally intensive.
3. For each entry in each representation (5×4374) the three metrics are calculated, smoothed and correlation with the cosine is computed. The result of this process is a dataframe with 60 correlation columns, one for every parameter-metric-representation group.
4. boxplots are generated, filtering the dataframe based on what parameter is modulated and grouped by modulation balance between first and second modulation and modulation offset, i.e., the phase of modulation 2. For this tables are also necessary to evaluate the influence of other modulations on the one that it is being tracked, for this tasks boxplots would be too many and difficult to navigate so only the average is used.

5.3 Results

In order to understand the results boxplots have been produced, each boxplot is built with the data points of a single representation, a single metric and a single

modulation target, it is important to remember that two parameters are being modulated in each sample, and the boxplots consider a data point valid if one of the two is the one selected. Thus the boxplots are not useful to understand how modulations interact based on the combination of parameters, for this purpose tables are presented in the next section. Boxplots are used to understand how the balance between the two modulations and the phase of the second modulation influence the tracking of the first. The boxplots have correlation on the y axis and either balance or offset on the x axis. All the plots are examinable in the notebook([sonic-trajectories/blob/main/study-2.ipynb](#)).

5.3.1 Example boxplots

The following examples are two the boxplots of filter cutoff tracking in music2latent, the entries for used are the ones that contain filter cutoff modulation, which are half of the dataset (2187), which is the case for any specific parameter modulation. These plots don't take into account what is the other modulated parameter, they are all aggregated. Each plot is explained in detail in the following paragraphs.

Figure 20: music2latent filter cutoff modulation against second modulation offset

In Figure 20 the x axis is the offset of the second modulation, that means that we always consider filter cutoff modulation having phase 0 and the modulation of the other parameter having phase $0, \frac{\pi}{2}, \pi$. It can be seen that the correlation doesn't vary a lot between the different metrics, to chose the best one the results of study 1 should be considered. It is clear that when the second modulation is in phase or shifted by π (inverted polarity) the tracking has performs better, getting close to

the results of study 1. When second modulation is shifted by $\frac{\pi}{2}$ the performance degrades drastically meaning that if the modulations are not synchronous the disturbance is very high and filter cutoff becomes very hard to track with those metric in music2latent.

Figure 21: music2latent filter cutoff modulation against modulation amount

In Figure 21 the x axis is the balance between the filter cutoff modulation and the modulation on the other parameter, aggregated. As for the first plot in order to choose the best metric the results of study 1 should be considered. In this case the plot shows that the difference at the various degrees of balance is not really relevant and the cutoff tracking is not really influenced by the balance between the modulation amounts.

5.3.2 Tables

In this section, we present tables for each parameter and their combinations. These tables highlight the most important results of the experiment, as they show how different parameters interact and interfere with each other's tracking. Each table includes only half of the samples, those containing one chosen parameter modulation. In the tables, each column shows the average correlation of the primary modulation when a secondary modulation (listed in that column) is also present.

For the frequency modulation tracking results (Table 2), the table shows that CQT is the best performing representation, which is aligned with the results of study 1. The best metrics are cosine and distances, and the most disturbing modulation

	freq amp	freq cutoff	freq shape	all freq
spectrum magnitude	0.63	0.57	0.59	0.59
spectrum distances	0.64	0.60	0.61	0.61
spectrum similarity	0.63	0.63	0.55	0.60
dac magnitude	0.51	0.52	0.49	0.51
dac distances	0.51	0.45	0.42	0.46
dac similarity	0.54	0.49	0.43	0.49
music2latent magnitude	0.55	0.56	0.55	0.56
music2latent distances	0.63	0.57	0.57	0.59
music2latent similarity	0.61	0.58	0.59	0.59
cqt magnitude	0.64	0.57	0.53	0.58
cqt distances	0.69	0.65	0.63	0.65
cqt similarity	0.69	0.64	0.61	0.65
mfcc magnitude	0.63	0.61	0.52	0.59
mfcc distances	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60
mfcc similarity	0.62	0.60	0.59	0.61

Table 2: Frequency averages

is oscillator waveshape. Modulating the waveshape means change the harmonic content, thus the content in the higher dimensions of the representation varies a lot, and this explains the disturb.

The amplitude modulation table (Table 3) shows that CQT magnitude is the best metric to track amplitude, this is coherent with study 1, the most influential secondary modulation is frequency, and this happens because of how the energy is distributed is spread across the bins and how the norm is calculated. Amplitude is overall the easiest modulation to track, and it is quite understandable that calculating total energy per frame, which is what the norm is doing works well for this no matter what the secondary modulation happens to be.

As for study 1, MFCC magnitude is the best at tracking frequency cutoff, this is not surprising since MFCC describe the overall shape of the spectrum which is what we are changing when modulating the filter’s cutoff frequency. The most impactful secondary modulation is amplitude, which is not surprising since it greatly impacts the first coefficients, which are often the ones that contain the information related to a soft filter like the one we are using.

	freq amp	amp cutoff	amp shape	all amp
spectrum magnitude	0.76	0.67	0.72	0.72
spectrum distances	0.68	0.66	0.70	0.68
spectrum similarity	0.72	0.78	0.80	0.77
dac magnitude	0.49	0.46	0.50	0.48
dac distances	0.58	0.73	0.73	0.68
dac similarity	0.59	0.76	0.71	0.69
music2latent magnitude	0.56	0.62	0.66	0.61
music2latent distances	0.75	0.83	0.83	0.80
music2latent similarity	0.75	0.85	0.83	0.81
cqt magnitude	0.83	0.89	0.89	0.87
cqt distances	0.59	0.79	0.75	0.71
cqt similarity	0.65	0.76	0.74	0.71
mfcc magnitude	0.85	0.80	0.86	0.84
mfcc distances	0.45	0.54	0.53	0.51
mfcc similarity	0.45	0.62	0.59	0.55

Table 3: Amplitude averages

Shape modulation (Table 5) is the one that shows the biggest difference with study one, CQT distances, which was the best metric in study one, performs significantly worse when other other modulations are in place and the best performing metric is now music2latent distances, significantly more resistant. The most disturbing modulation is frequency, which makes sense since what is to be tracked in music2latent is the relative structure of spectral peaks and frequency moves them around.

Summary table

Table 6 summarizes the results of study 2, the absolute best metric n average is MFCC magnitude but that’s mostly due to its performance at tracking filter cutoff. Better all rounders are CQT magnitude and music2latent distances.

5.4 Discussion

This study shows a drastic decrease in performance at tracking specific modulations with those metrics compared to study one. The interaction between the various modulations interferes a lot with the tracking of most single parameters, with the main exceptions being amplitude modulation across most of representations and

	freq cutoff	amp cutoff	cutoff shape	all cutoff
spectrum magnitude	0.67	0.58	0.69	0.64
spectrum distances	0.61	0.54	0.67	0.61
spectrum similarity	0.71	0.65	0.78	0.71
dac magnitude	0.45	0.38	0.55	0.46
dac distances	0.47	0.58	0.63	0.56
dac similarity	0.49	0.65	0.59	0.57
music2latent magnitude	0.53	0.65	0.59	0.59
music2latent distances	0.56	0.73	0.72	0.67
music2latent similarity	0.59	0.71	0.69	0.66
cqt magnitude	0.64	0.68	0.81	0.71
cqt distances	0.51	0.58	0.69	0.59
cqt similarity	0.53	0.54	0.70	0.59
mfcc magnitude	0.82	0.74	0.85	0.80
mfcc distances	0.43	0.39	0.59	0.47
mfcc similarity	0.43	0.44	0.59	0.49

Table 4: Filter cutoff averages

MFCCs for tracking filter cutoff.

Traditional representations are still a very valid way to track modulations, especially CQT, but this study reveals that metrics are quite harder to pick in a more realistic scenario. Where distances were performing as a good all rounder now both magnitude and similarity are needed, which has the upside that different metrics correlate to different things but also that there’s no single metric that conveys the overall groove.

Neural representations, music2latent in particular, are much more resistant and the performance is not impacted as much as for traditional representation. This could be a very interesting feature of those type of representations, but testing on a more varied dataset is needed to confirm its usefulness.

	freq shape	amp shape	cutoff shape	all shape
spectrum magnitude	0.52	0.52	0.49	0.51
spectrum distances	0.49	0.53	0.50	0.51
spectrum similarity	0.52	0.62	0.61	0.59
dac magnitude	0.46	0.43	0.48	0.45
dac distances	0.37	0.57	0.55	0.50
dac similarity	0.39	0.60	0.57	0.52
music2latent magnitude	0.56	0.59	0.60	0.58
music2latent distances	0.59	0.69	0.68	0.66
music2latent similarity	0.54	0.68	0.64	0.62
cqt magnitude	0.56	0.65	0.63	0.61
cqt distances	0.51	0.59	0.56	0.55
cqt similarity	0.50	0.53	0.51	0.51
mfcc magnitude	0.57	0.65	0.64	0.62
mfcc distances	0.42	0.41	0.45	0.43
mfcc similarity	0.41	0.44	0.44	0.43

Table 5: Wave shape averages

	frequency	amp	cutoff	shape	overall
cqt distances	0.65	0.71	0.59	0.55	0.63
cqt magnitude	0.58	0.87	0.71	0.61	0.69
cqt similarity	0.65	0.71	0.59	0.51	0.62
dac distances	0.46	0.68	0.56	0.50	0.55
dac magnitude	0.51	0.48	0.46	0.45	0.48
dac similarity	0.49	0.69	0.57	0.52	0.57
mfcc distances	0.60	0.51	0.47	0.43	0.50
mfcc magnitude	0.59	0.84	0.80	0.62	0.71
mfcc similarity	0.61	0.55	0.49	0.43	0.52
music2latent distances	0.59	0.80	0.67	0.66	0.68
music2latent magnitude	0.56	0.61	0.59	0.58	0.58
music2latent similarity	0.59	0.81	0.66	0.62	0.67
spectrum distances	0.61	0.68	0.61	0.51	0.60
spectrum magnitude	0.59	0.72	0.64	0.51	0.62
spectrum similarity	0.60	0.77	0.71	0.59	0.67

Table 6: Study 2 overall summary, best are in **bold**

Chapter 6

Conclusions and discussion

6.1 Overview

This work explored sonic trajectories as a way to represent continuous changes in sound, moving beyond onset-based analysis to capture variations in amplitude, pitch, timbre, and spectral shape. A trajectory extraction framework was proposed, combining traditional signal-processing representations and neural latent spaces with simple but robust metrics. Exploratory experiments established the feasibility of the approach, and two systematic studies evaluated the capacity of different representations and metrics to follow both isolated and interacting modulations. Taken together, the results highlight both the promise of trajectory-based methods for music information retrieval and sound analysis, and the challenges that remain when dealing with overlapping or multidimensional changes.

6.2 Representations

The results across both studies show that representation choice has a decisive influence on trajectory extraction. Traditional representations remain highly competitive: Constant-Q Transform proved reliable in tracking both frequency- and amplitude-related changes, while MFCC magnitudes excelled at following filter cut-off modulations. These methods, despite their age, continue to provide robust base-

lines. Neural latent spaces, such as Music2Latent, offered comparable performance with the advantage of reduced dimensionality, suggesting that MIR-oriented models can capture relevant perceptual changes efficiently. In contrast, the Descript Audio Codec, designed for compression rather than analysis, performed consistently poorly, reinforcing the idea that task-specific design matters more than raw representational power.

6.3 Metrics

Across representations, different metrics revealed different sensitivities. Distances between vectors were generally the most stable, particularly when tracking spectral changes like filter cutoff or oscillator shape. Magnitudes were strongly influenced by amplitude, performing well when energy-related variations were dominant but less reliably elsewhere. Cosine similarity proved effective in certain conditions but degraded significantly in the presence of subtle or overlapping modulations. These differences suggest that no single metric can serve as a universal solution; instead, a combination of complementary measures may be required to capture the full spectrum of sonic trajectories.

6.4 First Study: Single Modulations

The first study provided a controlled baseline by evaluating single modulations of synthetic sounds. Each modulation, applied to amplitude, frequency, filter cutoff, or oscillator shape, was tested in isolation, allowing direct measurement of how well different representations and metrics aligned with the ground-truth trajectories. Results showed that for isolated modulations, traditional representations performed best: CQT distances consistently tracked frequency and amplitude modulations, while MFCC magnitudes were highly effective for filter cutoff. Music2Latent, though not outperforming CQT or MFCC, showed competitive results with far lower dimensionality, indicating its efficiency. The Descript Audio Codec underperformed, confirming its lack of suitability for fine-grained modulation tracking. Importantly, this study established the sensitivity of different methods under idealized conditions,

providing a clear benchmark before moving to more complex cases.

6.5 Second Study: Double Modulations

The second study extended the framework to double modulations, introducing simultaneous variations in two parameters. This created conditions where trajectories interacted, overlapped, or interfered with one another, better reflecting the complexity of real sonic evolution. Results demonstrated that tracking accuracy generally decreased compared to the single-modulation case, with interferences particularly strong when one modulation affected spectral shape (e.g., oscillator mix) alongside another. Nonetheless, some patterns emerged: CQT again provided robust results, though its performance degraded in certain combinations; Music2Latent showed resilience in amplitude-related tasks, suggesting potential for disentangling trajectories in latent space; and metrics based on distances remained the most stable across conditions. The study highlighted that while single modulations can be tracked reliably, simultaneous modulations remain a significant challenge, requiring more sophisticated methods for disentanglement.

6.6 Future Directions

The findings suggest several avenues for further work. First, representation learning tailored to trajectory extraction could improve performance, particularly by designing neural encoders with higher temporal resolution and disentangled latent dimensions. Second, metric development remains open: hybrid approaches combining statistical correlation with perceptual models may better capture complex modulations. Third, extending the test bench to polyphonic or real-world audio would provide stronger validity and highlight practical limitations. Finally, creative applications, such as trajectory-based controllers for live performance, generative music systems, or interactive sound design, represent promising directions where the methods developed here could directly impact artistic practice.

List of Figures

1	music2latent vector magnitudes easily tracks amplitude	17
2	CQT shows some repeating patterns	17
3	DAC clearly moves when pitch is not stable	18
4	music2latent vector magnitudes easily tracks inharmonic sines over noise	18
5	Low pass filter affects CQT distances	19
6	Low pass filter impact on music2latent magnitude	19
7	music2latent vector magnitudes easily tracks soft clipping	19
8	Impact of fm amount on CQT magnitude	20
9	Impact of fm amount on music2latent similarity	20
10	cqt vector magnitudes	20
11	music2latent magnitudes	21
12	DAC magnitudes	21
13	music2latent filter cutoff modulation against modulation amount . . .	28
14	music2latent filter cutoff modulation against amplitude	29
15	music2latent filter cutoff modulation against frequency	29
16	music2latent filter cutoff modulation against oscillator wave shape . .	30
17	music2latent filter cutoff modulation against filter cutoff frequency . .	30
18	CQT and frequency modulation	32
19	MFCC and filter cutoff modulation	32
20	music2latent filter cutoff modulation against second modulation offset	39
21	music2latent filter cutoff modulation against modulation amount . . .	40
22	Correlation histogram	56

23	Correlation for generalized model	57
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List of Tables

1	Study 1 summary table	31
2	Study 2 frequency summary	41
3	Study 2 amplitude summary	42
4	Study 2 cutoff summary	43
5	Study 2 shape summary	44
6	Study 2 summary	44

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Appendix A

Linear Analysis of Modulation Representation

Jupyter notebook available at: [sonic-trajectories/blob/main/study-3.ipynb](https://sonic-trajectories.github.io/blob/main/study-3.ipynb)

This appendix details a third study, an extension of the metric-based methods in Studies 1 and 2. The main goal is to find if control parameter modulations can be linearly reconstructed from the vectors of an audio representation.

This analysis asks two questions:

1. For a single audio sample, can a linear combination of a representation's dimensions reconstruct the ground-truth modulation signal? How good is this reconstruction?
2. If these linear combinations exist, do they work for other samples? Is a filter cutoff sweep, for example, always encoded in the same dimensions for different sounds?

A.1 Setup

A.1.1 Dataset

The dataset for this study is significantly different from the previous, it consists of 1000 10s (more than 3h) minisynt synthesized samples with random sub audio modulations. Samples have 1,2,3 or 4 concurrent modulations, all different with each other. This ensure the maximum variety possible for this minisynt class, which means that if the method works on those minisynt sounds it works on all of them. The dataset is available at huggingface.co/datasets/inspektral/minisynt1k-sub-points-v1 and renderable via minisynt (see notebook).

A.1.2 Methodology

The method is a two-stage analysis using linear regression. The assumption is that the modulation signal M (a time series) is a linear combination of the dimensions of the audio representation R (a matrix of time frames x dimensions). The relationship is:

$$M \approx R \cdot w$$

Where:

- M is the ground-truth modulation vector (length T).
- R is the representation matrix ($T \times D$).
- w is a weight vector (length D).

The optimal weight vector w is found using ordinary least squares (OLS), which minimizes the squared difference between the real modulation M and the predicted one $R \cdot w$.

A.1.3 Stage 1: Per-Sample Model Fitting

In the first stage, the process is applied to each audio sample. For each sample i , with representation R_i and modulation M_i , a weight vector w_i is computed.

The model performance is measured with the Pearson correlation between the ground-truth modulation M_i and the reconstructed modulation $R_i \cdot w_i$. A high correlation (close to 1.0) means the modulation is linear for that sample's representation.

A.1.4 Stage 2: Generalization with an Average Model

The second stage tests if the model generalizes. The weight vectors (w_i) for all samples with the same modulated parameter (e.g., filter cutoff) are averaged to create a single vector, w_{avg} :

$$w_{avg} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N w_i$$

This average vector is a general model for that parameter and representation. Its performance is tested on each sample j . Performance is the Pearson correlation between the ground-truth M_j and the reconstructed modulation $R_j \cdot w_{avg}$.

Good performance implies the modulation is encoded in the same way for all samples. Poor performance suggests the encoding is context-dependent, using different dimensions or weights for each sample.

A.2 Results

The results from the two-stage analysis answer the initial questions.

A.2.1 Per-Sample Model Performance

The analysis shows that for any sample, a linear combination of dimensions can be found to reconstruct the modulation. As shown in Figure 22, the correlation scores

for the per-sample models were close to 1.0 for most parameters and representations. This shows that the modulation information is present and linear within the representation’s dimensions.

Figure 22: Correlation histograms for per-sample model fitting. For all four modulation types in the ‘music2latent’ representation, the correlations are heavily skewed towards 1.0, indicating near-perfect linear reconstruction.

A.2.2 Generalization Model Performance

The performance of the average model depended on the modulated parameter and the representation.

- **Good Generalization:** Sometimes, the average model performed well, which means the encoding was consistent. For example, amplitude modulation worked well, as most representations capture energy.
- **Poor Generalization:** In other cases, the model’s performance was much worse. The results varied, with poor results for many samples. For example, the ‘music2latent’ model for filter cutoff gave varied results, while its model for oscillator shape performed poorly overall.

Figure 23: Correlation distribution for the generalized average model on ‘music2latent’. The filter cutoff model (left) shows a wide, inconsistent distribution of correlations, while the oscillator shape model (right) performs poorly overall, with most correlations below 0.4.

This shows that while the modulation is linear in each sample, the dimensions and weights change for each sample. A change in base frequency, for example, can make the representation use different dimensions to encode a filter sweep.

A.3 Discussion

These findings add to the results of Studies 1 and 2. The simple metrics of magnitude, distance, and similarity show general change, but this study shows the information is more structured.

The near-perfect per-sample result is important. It suggests that even in complex latent spaces, the representation of features has structure; it is linear on a per-sample basis.

The mixed results of the average model are also important. It answers questions about interpretability and consistency. To be interpretable, a feature like filter cutoff should be represented in the same way. The results show this is not always true; the encoding depends on context. This is a key problem in using audio representations: a feature can be represented differently for each sound.